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An optimum electrochemical production method of few-layers and few-defective graphene

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Abstract

Among the different synthesizing method of graphene, besides having a most suitable and cost-effective method, it is essential to have high-quality graphene. For this reason, the effects of the cathode electrode, the time and type of voltage variation, dispersion time, the electrolyte salt and washing solvent on process performance of electrochemical exfoliation of graphite (EE-G) were investigated. Here, we show great promise for few-layer and few-defective graphene by optimum EE-G. The most suitable condition to produce graphene is performing the process in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$. Moreover, the NaOH as salt is suitable in the synthesis of graphene quantum dots. Raman analysis clearly showed the G, D band, and 2D band of carbon for samples.

Keywords: Graphene; Electrochemical Synthesis Method; Electrochemical Exfoliation; Raman Analysis.